

Global Monitoring and Retrievals of Atmospheric Aerosols and Clouds

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Abstract -- A knowledge of aerosol and cloud radiative properties and their variation in space and time is especially crucial to the understanding of the radiative forcing in all climate related studies. The role of clouds in modifying the Earth's radiation balance - albedo cooling effect in shortwave radiation and greenhouse warming effect in longwave radiation - is well recognized as a key source of uncertainty. Man-made processes, both burning of fossil fuels and biomass, generate greenhouse gases and aerosol particles. Directly, aerosol particles can scatter and absorb the sun light. Indirectly, these particles may serve as cloud condensation nuclei and alter cloud albedo. Ship tracks have provided intriguing examples of cloud albedo modification by anthropogenic aerosols. There has been a general concern that the potential climate forcing from the indirect effects of aerosol on clouds can be of comparable magnitude, but opposite in sign, to greenhouse gas radiative forcing.

Global monitoring of aerosol and cloud radiative effects relies on advanced Earth Observing Systems (e.g., NASA's EOS and NASDA's ADEOS). Key advances include simultaneous observation of radiation budget and aerosol/cloud properties, additional information on particle size, phase, and vertical layer structure. Comprehensive radiation models are used to develop retrieval algorithms. This paper presents an overview of the science and technique in remote sensing and retrievals of atmospheric aerosols and clouds. High quality multi-spectral imagery, together with nadir propagating lidar measurements, acquired from high altitude aircraft in many field experiments are served as examples for discussion.

EARTH OBSERVING SYSTEMS

Observations by remote sensing from space broaden our view and perception of the Earth Sciences, and permit for the first time a systematic view of the Earth. Current and future Earth observing satellites can provide opportunities for global monitoring and retrievals of atmospheric aerosols and clouds. For example, a comprehensive suite of instruments onboard the first Japanese ADEOS (ADvanced Earth Observing Satellite) was successfully launched and operated in orbit since August 1996; the first U.S. EOS (Earth Observing System) AM-1 is scheduled to launch in June 1998. These series of satellites, including those from other countries, form the basis for a comprehensive International EOS and assure the capability of continuous operation for at least 15 years. Sustained observations will allow scientists to monitor Earth's climate variables over time to determine trends and to estimate magnitudes.

It has been a long-standing goal to quantify global cloud and aerosol properties from spaceborne observations, such as cloud cover, cloud particle thermodynamic phase, cloud optical thickness and effective particle radius, cloud top altitude and temperature, aerosol optical thickness, and aerosol columnar mass concentration, etc. The development of retrieving atmospheric aerosol and cloud properties can benefit greatly from using the multi-spectral, multi-angle, and high spatial and temporal resolution EOS data. For example, simultaneous determination of cloud optical thickness and effective particle radius can be achieved by inverting visible and near-infrared radiometric data, with the help of forward radiative transfer calculations. The underlying principle on which these techniques are based is the fact that the reflectance of clouds at a non-absorbing band in the visible wavelength region is primarily a function of the cloud optical thickness, whereas the reflectance at a water (or ice) absorbing band in the near-infrared is primarily a function of cloud particle size. More sophisticated approaches in retrieving cloud properties may utilize more spectral information. For example, the MODIS (MODerate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer, EOS AM-1) algorithms (King et al. 1996) apply seven bands (0.65, 0.86, 1.24, 1.64, 2.13, 3.75, and 11.03 μm) in cloud retrievals for optimal performance. Different MODIS bands are used for different surface types (i.e., 0.65 μm over land, 0.86 μm over ocean, and 1.24 μm over snow/ice) to enhance retrieval sensitivity; and others for atmospheric corrections.

Similarly, the retrievals of aerosol properties can take advantage of the MODIS wide spectral range and high spatial resolution. Using the shortwave infrared bands (e.g., 2.1 and 3.7 μm) to identify dark objects and to estimate their reflectance at the visible bands (e.g., 0.47, and 0.66 μm), the aerosol optical thickness and mass concentration can be retrieved from measured radiance field (Kaufman and Tanré 1996). An alternative method is utilizing the ultraviolet techniques (e.g., channels available in Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer, ADEOS), in which the radiative signatures of biomass burning aerosols are spectrally dependent as opposed to clouds and background environments. By taking the reflectivity differences between ozone non-absorbing wavelengths, the effects of multiple scattering between the Rayleigh molecules and aerosols are dominant and can be represented as a measure of the abundance of aerosols in the atmosphere (e.g., Hsu et al. 1996).

DISCUSSIONS

For many Earth remote sensing applications, cloud de-

Fig. 1. Results of reflectance, brightness temperature, cloud and cloud shadow masks derived from the MAS measurements obtained on 7 June 1995 during ARM-CAS field experiment

tection (or derivation of a cloud mask) is vital because the Earth is frequently covered by various types of clouds. The cloud mask indicates whether a given field of view has an unobstructed view of the Earth surface, or whether the pixel is cloud free but affected by cloud shadows or thick aerosol (Ackerman et al. 1996). Spectral information from up to 14 MODIS channels (visible, near-IR and IR) is used, for the first time. Below, we use the 50-channel MAS (MODIS Airborne Simulator, 0.47 - 14.35 μm) measurements for discussions. With their high spatial resolution (~ 50 m at ER-2 20 km altitude), MAS measurements help to assess ways of convolving small scale variations to the larger scales typical of satellite sensors (like MODIS, with its primary resolution of 1 km) and serve as a prototype for cloud mask development.

Figure 1 shows the results of cloud and cloud shadow

masks, together with 0.657 μm reflectance and 11.02 μm brightness temperature measurements from ARM-CAS (Arctic Radiation Measurements in Column Atmosphere-surface System, conducted in Alaska and Beaufort Sea area in June 1995) experiment. Images of a convective cumulonimbus cloud (lower center) surrounded by lower level water clouds on the northern foothills of the Brooks Range, Alaska, were acquired on 7 June 1995. The first panel on the left (0.657 μm) shows high contrast between the optically thick (and therefore bright) cumulonimbus cloud, diffuse cirrus anvil, and remnants of the snow pack lying in ravines and topographic depressions (lower right of image), less reflective altocumulus clouds (upper and center portion of image), and dark tundra. The second panel (11.02 μm) appears quite cold (low radiance) in the coldest portion of the cumulonimbus cloud (-50°C), warmer at the top of the altocumulus cloud (-18°C), where the cloud must be composed

Fig. 2. Results of spectral reflectance and cloud mask, with indication of heavy aerosol loading (or aerosol mask), derived from the MAS measurements obtained on 4 September 1995 during SCAR-B field experiment.

of supercooled water rather than ice (according to the 1.609 and 1.879 μm channels, not shown), and warmest at the surface (+17°C). By comparing to the 0.657 and 11.02 μm images, the detection of cloud shadow mask (blue color in the third panel) and cloud mask (white color in the last panel) was very successful.

In the springtime burning season in Brazil, thick haze is generated by burning of cerrado and primary forest, producing much haze as well as burning and smoldering fires and clouds. Figure 2 shows an example of the application of the cloud mask (clear sky with aerosol loading) to such biomass burning aerosols in SCAR-B (Smoke, Clouds, And Radiation - Brazil, August - September 1995). At 0.55 μm it is difficult to see the ground due to the heavy smoke and aerosol from extensive biomass burning. At 0.87 μm (second panel from left), on the other hand, surface reflectance is high and the haze is transparent, except where the ground has already been burned and is dark from burn scars. At 2.14 μm (third panel), the burn scars are again quite reflective, as if often the case over pavement in cities. The resultant aerosol mask (last panel) was derived from a combination of tests on 12 different MAS channels. Most of the scene is classified as high confident clear with heavy aerosol

(red in aerosol mask), and correctly noting that this scene is not composed of cloud as suggested from 0.55 μm band.

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